
DR. LUCY OJODE, CPA(K)

Associate Professor
Texas Southern University
Jesse H. Jones School of Business
Department of Business Administration
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Education

Doctor of Philosophy (2000)

Business Administration

Major: Strategic Management

Minor: International Business

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, IL.

Dissertation Title: *A resource-based view of strategic alliances: Organizational capabilities, governance, and performance*

Master of Business Administration (1989)

Major: Management Science

Minor: Finance

University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya.

Bachelor of Commerce (1987)

Major: Accounting

University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya.

Academic Work Experience

2015- Present **Professor**, Texas Southern University, Texas
2008- 2015 **Associate Professor**, Texas Southern University, Texas
2004 - 2008 **Assistant Professor**, Texas Southern University, Texas
2000 - 2003 **Assistant Professor** of International Business, Indiana University, Indiana
2003 Summer **Visiting Professor**, United States International University, Nairobi, Kenya
2003 Summer **Visiting MBA Theses Advisor**, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya
1999-2000 **Lecturer** in International Business, Indiana University, Indiana
1995-1999 **Teaching Assistant**, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Illinois
1989-1994 **Lecturer**, Dept. of Agric. Econ & Agribusiness, Egerton University, Kenya

Professional Training

Certified Public Accountant-Kenya

Institute of Certified Public Accountants of Kenya, Nairobi, Kenya

Non-Academic Work Experience

2010-Present	Adelphos Bible Church: Director and Administrator
1988-Present	Ojode & Associates CPA(K): Investment and Business Consultant
1991-1993	Kenya Accountants and Secretaries National Examination Board (KASNEB): CPA Examiner
1992	Consortium for International Development (CID)\USA International Development (USAID): Consultant
1992	USAID\Egerton University Agricultural Management Project: Executive Trainer
1987	Pannel-Bellhouse-Mwangi CPA(K): Audit Assistant

Research

Interests

Business Strategy, Strategic Alliances, Competitive Advantage
Global Business, Multinational Enterprises, Emerging Markets,

Teaching Interests

Strategic Management, Business Strategy/Policy
International Management, Global Business

Refereed Publications

Desai M., Desai K., & **Ojode L.** (2015): "Supply Chain Risk Management Framework: A Fishbone Analysis Approach" *SAM Advanced Management Journal* (forthcoming).

Ojode, L. (2014b): "Top-Bottom of the Pyramid Collaborative Engagement" Chapter 45 in Taras, Vasyl & Gonzalez-Perez, Maria Alejandra (Eds.) *Handbook of Experiential Learning in International Business*, Palgrave Macmillan, Pg 743-759.

Ojode, L. (2014a): "Integrated Experiential Learning: Africa and the United States" Chapter 5 in Taras, Vasyl & Gonzalez-Perez, Maria Alejandra (Eds.) *Handbook of Experiential Learning in International Business*, Palgrave Macmillan, Pg 51-64.

- Oke, A., Walumbwa F., Yan T., Idiagbon-Oke, & **Ojode** L. (2014): "Linking socio-economic factors with technology adoption in three emerging economies of Sub-Saharan Africa." *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, Vol. 25 (1), Pg 49-68.
www.emeraldinsight.com/1741-038X.html.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K., **Ojode** L., & Woldu H.G. (2011): "Cutting the umbilical cord: The changing determinants and patterns of Sub-Saharan African trade." *Journal of International Management Studies*, Vol. 6 (1), Pg 129-138. <http://www.jimsjournal.org/pi.html>.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K., **Ojode** L., & Woldie M. (2010): "Achieving goal congruence between the objectives of multinational enterprises (MNEs) and developing countries (DCs)." *Journal of International Management Studies*, Vol. 5 (1), Pg 138-146.
<http://www.jimsjournal.org/pi.html>.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K. & **Ojode** L. (2009): "The effect of governance quality on foreign direct investment flows into Sub-Saharan Africa." *Journal of International Management Studies*, Vol. 4 (2), Pg 222-230. <http://www.jimsjournal.org/pi.html>.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K., **Ojode**, L. & Desai M. (2008): "An inter-temporal comparison of the determinants of non-extractive US direct foreign investment in Sub-Saharan Africa." *The Journal of Global Business Management*, Vol. 4 (2), Pg 14-23.
<http://www.jgbm.org/index.files/Page995.html>.
- Ojode**, L. (2007b): "Faces of business ethics and international tobacco regulation," a video case documentary. Published: September @
<http://www.tsu.edu/academics/business/trans/displaySingleMsgRpt.asp?id=919&type=6>
- Ojode**, L. (2007a): "Nurturing a stakeholder oriented strategic planning culture" in *Strategic Planning for Global Competitiveness Symposium*, Claiborne C.B. (Ed), Jesse H. Jones School of Business, July 30-August 7, Working Papers, Pg 6-11.
- Ojode**, L. (2006b): "Leveraging technological capabilities across polarized cultures: Shanghai Delco Electronics Limited." *Asian Case Research Journal*, Vol. 10 (1), Pg 27-54.
<http://www.worldscinet.com/acrj/10/1001/S02189275061001.html>.
- Ojode**, L. (2006a): "Tobacco business and regulation in the developing markets: The case of British American Tobacco (BAT) in East Africa." *Journal of African Business* Vol.7 (1/2), Pg 31-56.
- Ojode**, L. (2004): "The impact of horizontal strategic alliances on the U.S. steel industry" *Journal of Business Strategies*, Vol. 21 (2), Pg 149-178.
http://www.allbusiness.com/business_planning/business_structures/3501628-1.html.
- Walumbwa F., Wu C., & **Ojode** L. (2004): "Gender and instructional outcomes: The mediating role of leadership style" *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 23 (2), Pg 124-140.

Desai M., Desai K., & **Ojode** L. (2004): "A global information technology model: Business applications in developing economies case studies" *Information Management and Computer Security*, Vol. 12 (5), Pg 401-410.

Conference Presentations and Proceedings

Ojode, L., Woldie, M., & Olaly, W. (2015): "Developing Leadership and Managerial Expertise in Africa: Teaching Business Decision Making Using Experiential Learning" The 4th International Conference on HRM and the Management of Organizations in Africa, Nairobi, Kenya. August 26-28.

Desai M., Desai K., & **Ojode** L. (2015): "Supply Chain Risk Management Framework: A Fishbone Analysis Approach" *Society for Advancement of Management International Conference Proceedings* (forthcoming).

Ojode L. & Woldie M. (2014): "Teaching Undergraduates Business Decision Making: Theory-Practice Hybridization" Southwestern Business Administration Teaching (SWBAT) Conference, Houston, TX

Buchan, N.R, Rolf, R.J., **Ojode**, L. & Orinda, M. (2014). "Untangling the Influence of Globalization and Ethnic Fractionalization on National Cooperation" *Academy of International Business Conference*, Vancouver, Canada. June 24-26.
https://aib.msu.edu/events/2014/pdfs/AIB2014_Proceedings.pdf, Pg 137.

Ojode, L. (2013) "Integrated Experiential Learning in a Global Environment" Presented in the X-Culture interactive poster session at the 3rd Annual International Creative Learning for Innovation (CAL4INO) Conference, London, UK. December 29.
<http://www.cal4ino.com>.

Ojode L. (2013): "Integrated experiential learning in a global environment" Southwestern Business Administration Teaching (SWBAT) Conference, Houston, TX.

Ojode, L. (2013): "New old Frontier: Opportunities for America's Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Africa" *Creating a Collaborative Research Culture*, Texas Southern University Research Week, April, Houston, TX.

Woldie M., Ofori-Brobby K., York G. & **Ojode** L. (2012): "The joys and scholarship of education: Has online teaching helped improve students' classroom performance?" *Southwestern Business Administration Teaching (SWBAT) Conference*, Houston, TX.

Ojode L., Sun H., & Caussin M. (2012): "Incorporating foreign languages in the business curriculum: Peer learning among foreign languages and business students," *SWBAT Conference*, Houston, TX.

- Ojode** L., Ofori-Brobbeey K. & Desai M. (2010): “Connecting with students: Practicals of executive skills” *SWBAT* Conference, Houston, TX.
- Ojode**, L. (2009): The principles and practices of management (edited collection of MGMT 636: *Theories of Management* class papers): “A view of some corporate practices in America—the case of Bechtel Corporation” by Borten S., Cooksey Y., & Holiday E.; “Strategic planning in American autos: Managerial hubris at GM?” by Thompson T., Domoneck O., & Kirven T.; “Substantive global and alliance strategies: A luxury or necessity for American automakers?” by Jones-Lewis A., Campbell T., & Handy J., *SWBAT* Conference, Houston, TX.
- Ojode**, L. (2009): “Strategic planning for global competitiveness” Seminar at the Fourth JHJ Global Commerce & Mickey Leland Centers Symposium, Houston, TX.
- Ojode**, L. (2007): “Strategic planning for global competitiveness” Seminar at the First JHJ Global Commerce & Mickey Leland Centers Symposium, Houston, TX.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K. & **Ojode** L. (2007): “Global Challenges: Governance and Foreign Direct Investment in Africa and South America” *Society for Advancement of Management* Conference Proceedings.
- Ojode** L. & Ofori-Brobbeey K. (2006): “Governance and Foreign Direct Investment in Sub-Saharan Africa,” *International Academy of African Business and Development* Conference, Vol. VII, Pg 167-172.
- Ofori-Brobbeey K. & **Ojode**, L. (2006): “Do the Old Axioms Still Hold? Re-examining the Role of Fiscal Policies in FDI Flows” *Society for Advancement of Management* Conference, Pg 687-704.
- Ojode**, L. (2006): “Making executives of undergraduates: Using textbook and computer simulation to teach real-time executive decision making” *SWBAT* Conf., Houston, TX.
- Ojode** L. & Ogara E. (2005): “World Health Organization’s Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) Readiness: The Health and Business of Kenyan Tobacco Farmers and Leaf Suppliers,” *International Academy of African Business and Development* Conference, Vol. VI (1), Pg 478-486.
- Ojode**, L. (2003): “Murky foreign direct investment environment: The case of British American Tobacco (BAT) in East Africa” *International Academy of African Business and Development* Annual meeting, London, UK.
- Ojode**, L. (2002): “Karpark Inc. goes to Mexico” *Annual Midwest Academy of Management case colloquium*, Indianapolis, IN.
- Ojode**, L. (2001): “International Business” seminar to entrepreneurs at the first North Central *Indiana Technology and Entrepreneurship* conference, Kokomo, IN.
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- Ojode, L.** (2000): "Gender stereotype and instructors' leadership behavior: Transformational and transactional leadership." *Midwest Academy of Management 2000 Annual Conference*, Chicago, IL.
<http://www.sba.muohio.edu/management/mwAcademy/2000/Session#10>
- Ojode L.** (1999): "Eyeing the bottom-line: Value-creative alignment of resource characteristics to alliance governance." *Midwest Academy of Management 1999 Annual Conference*, Lincoln, NE. <http://www.sba.muohio.edu/management/mwAcademy/1999/Session#16>.
- Ojode L. & Walumbwa F.** (1999): "Developing human capital for the evolving work environment: Transactional and transformational leadership within instructional setting." *Midwest Academy of Management Annual Conference*, Lincoln, Nebraska.
<http://www.sba.muohio.edu/management/mwAcademy/1999/Session#20>.
- Walumbwa F. & **Ojode L.** (1999): "Millennial challenges in educational management and leadership: Female and male students' perception of professorial leadership styles." In B. Hindrichs and K. Klenke (Eds.), *Association of Management/International Association of Management Proceedings*. Vol.17 (1), Pg 291-298. Chesapeake, VI: Maxilian Press Publishers.
- Ojode, L.** (1998): "Organizational restructuring, capabilities, and strategic alliances: Who gains?" *Midwest Academy of Management 1998 Annual Conference* (Disk #3: MWPROC98.52.doc), Kansas City, Missouri:
<http://www.umkc.edu/html/news/1998/0403.html>.
- Ojode, L.** (1997): "A resource-based view of organizational reconfiguration: Building and leveraging competencies through strategic alliances" University of Illinois Seminar, Champaign, IL.
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Research in Progress

- Buchan N., Rolfe R., Ojode L., & Orinda M.: "Untangling the influence of globalization and ethnic fragmentation on cooperation"
- Ojode L. & Woldie M.: "Pearl at the Bottom of the Pyramid (BOP): Global opportunities for SMEs in emerging markets"
- Ojode L. & Woldie M.: "Teaching Undergraduates Business Decision Making: Theory-Practice Hybridization"
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Other Writings

Ojode, L. (2012): "Alliancing for Inner City *Survivor* and *Millennial* Generations." *Adelphos Bible Church*, <http://www.adelphoshouston.org/a1/index.php/publications>

Ojode, L. (1992): Entrepreneurship workbook for the *Center for Women Studies and Gender Analysis* at Egerton University, Kenya.

Professional Initiatives and Development

Spring 2014. Completed TSU TLEC's workshop: *GradesFirst* Training, Houston, TX.

Summer 2013. Developed a unique Study Abroad business curriculum in which students learned at the University of Dar-es-salaam, attended an international symposium, had several corporate and cultural visits, and consulted with a local firm in Tanzania.

Spring 2013. Completed the Pacific Crest's *Student Success Institute* training, Houston, TX (www.pcrest.com).

Spring 2012. Completed TSU TLEC's workshops: *Assessment of Student Learning Outcomes*, and *Hands on Learning with Assessment of Student Outcomes*, Houston, TX.

Spring 2011. Completed the Blackboard Innovative Teaching Series: *Student Engagement in the Online Classroom* workshop.

Summer 2010. Faculty Development in International Business (FDIB) program in South Africa, Kenya, and Tanzania: Personally and partially funded by the University of Memphis Center for International Business Education and Research (CIBER) Global Business Studies (GBS) Study Abroad Scholarship:

<http://mooreschool.sc.edu/facultyandresearch/researchcenters/centerforinternationalbusinesseducationandresearchciber/facultydevelopment.aspx>

Summer 2007. Participated in the Faculty Development in International Business (FDIB), Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCU) Business and International Education (BIE) symposium, University of Memphis CIBER, Memphis, Tennessee.

Summer 2007. Completed *Globalization Seminars and Teaching International Business (IB)* Workshops, Memphis, Tennessee.

Summer 2003. Undertook Faculty Grant-in-Aid and Indiana University CIBER funded field research in Kenya. The research focused on the strategic response of tobacco firms to tightening global regulation (UN & the WHO passed the Framework Convention on Tobacco Control in May 2003).

Spring 2003. Participated in the Indiana *Consortium for International Programs (ICIP)* conference: "Teaching about Africa in the New Millennium," Bloomington, IN.

Summer 2002. Developed show-case online courses on the *Oncourse* platform at Indiana University that were used as best practice samples for faculty adoption at the Center for Teaching Excellence (CTE) Tech Camp workshops, Kokomo, IN.

Spring. Participated in the *Internationalizing Business Curricula* workshops in Austin, TX.

Fall 2001. Successfully completed the LERN Institute's *Online Teaching Course*.

Summer. Completed the Indiana University's CTE Tech Camp workshop on the *Oncourse* online learning program.

Spring. Completed *Global E-Business: Getting IT done* pedagogy workshop in Indianapolis, IN.

Awards

A 2014 Jesse H. Jones School of Business Seed Grant for Teaching Conference: "Teaching Undergraduates Business Decision Making: Theory-Practice Hybridization" \$1,000; **PI**

Harris County Council of Organizations Excellence Award (2013): For dedication and commitment to preparing Texas Southern University students for tomorrow.

A 2013 Jesse H. Jones School of Business Seed Grant for Teaching Conference: "Integrated experiential learning in a global environment" \$500; **PI**

A 2012 Seed Grant, Texas Southern University: "African Business Opportunities for America's Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs)" \$7,000; **PI**.

A 2010 Department of Education, through the University of Memphis Center for International Business Education and Research (CIBER), Faculty Development in International Business (FDIB) scholarship. About **\$10,000** for a study tour of Kenya, S. Africa, and Tanzania for the purpose of boosting international business research and the curriculum.

A 2007 University of Memphis CIBER scholarship award, \$1,195. For a revamping the international business curricula workshop in Memphis, TN. This workshop was part of the Department of Education's national efforts toward internationalizing business curricular (built on the 2002 Austin workshop and the basis for the 2010 international study tour).

A 2006 Seed Grant, Texas Southern University: "Faces of Business Ethics and International Tobacco Regulation". **\$5,160; PI**

A 2003 Indiana University Faculty Grant-in-Aid and CIBER Field Research Grant, \$3,595. The Kenya government boosted the grant with material resources, transportation, personnel, and field support for the field research in Kenya. **PI**

A 2002 Indiana University *CIBER* scholarship award for a workshop on internationalizing the business curricula. The scholarship paid for travel, board and lodge, and workshop material in Austin, TX.

University and Community Service

1. Member of TSU 2015 Faculty Senate Election Committee
 2. Chair of the TSU/JHJ Memorial Committee for the late Dr. W. K. Brobbey-Ofori
 3. A JHJ School of Business Faculty (AP/QP) Committee member
 4. Texas Southern University Chief Finance Officer Interviewer
 5. A Texas Southern University Faculty Senator
 6. A Texas Southern University General Education Subcommittee member.
 7. A Texas Southern University Student Engagement Through Technology (SETT) Mentor
 8. A JHJ School of Business Undergraduate Curriculum Committee member.
 9. A JHJ School of Business Assurance of Learning Committee member.
 10. A member of the Department of Business Administration's Curriculum Committee.
 11. A member of the Department of Business Administration's Grievance Committee.
 12. A Freshman Advisor in the Department of Business Administration.
 13. Founder and Director of Adelphos, a faith-based cross-cultural non-profit organization that networks to promote independence and global awareness among the disenfranchised in Houston's Third Ward. Ref: <http://www.adelphoshouston.org>.
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Professional Membership and Activities

Editorial Review Board member: Journal of African Business

Member of the Institute of Certified Public Accountants of Kenya (<http://www.icpak.com>)

Member of the World Affairs Council of Houston

Member and reviewer for the following professional organizations:

Academy of International Business (<http://www.aibworld.net/>)

Academy of Management (<http://www.acm.pace.edu/>)

International Academy of African Business and Development

Reviewed: *Digital Governance in Africa* Manuscript

